

Design and Optimization of Petrol Engine Flywheel for Variable Speeds

L.Haripriya¹, L.Mohanarao², Dr.J.Bala Bhaskara Rao³

P.G Students, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering and Technology

Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering and Technology

Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering and Technology

ABSTRACT - The flywheel stands as a pivotal component within the realm of machinery, serving as a reservoir for energy modulation, particularly in scenarios where energy supply and demand exhibit fluctuations. Embarking on the project to design a flywheel for a multi-cylinder petrol engine entails a meticulous process. Initially, a comprehensive 2D blueprint is crafted, incorporating intricate calculations to ensure precision. Subsequently, utilizing cutting-edge 3D modeling software like Catia, a parametric model of the flywheel is meticulously engineered, allowing for dynamic adjustments to suit varying operational parameters. An indispensable facet of the project involves assessing the forces exerted on the flywheel. Through meticulous calculations; these forces are quantified, enabling a deeper understanding of the structural demands placed upon the flywheel. This insight is further enriched through the utilization of Ansys, a renowned finite element analysis (FEA). In conclusion, the analysis results validate the accuracy of the design parameters. The strain exerted on the designed model, particularly at the fixing location, falls well within acceptable ranges, affirming the overall effectiveness and reliability of the design.

Keywords: Flywheel, stress, strain, elastic strain, deformation

I.INTRODUCTION

The flywheel, an essential component within the intricate machinery of internal combustion engines, assumes the form of a disk typically crafted from cast iron, aluminum, or zinc. Positioned steadfastly at one extremity of the crankshaft, its primary function lies in endowing the engine with inertia. Inertia, a fundamental property of matter, delineates the tendency of a physical body to persist in its state of rest or uniform motion unless acted upon by an external force. It's important to note that inertia itself isn't a force; rather, it embodies the innate resistance of matter to changes in its motion. In recent times, significant attention has been directed towards advancing mission critical technology programs, particularly in the realm of energy storage. One promising avenue involves the utilization of flywheels as a means of storing energy more efficiently compared to conventional rechargeable chemical batteries, while also offering distinct control advantages. Despite the concept of flywheels being centuries old, it is only with advancements in high-strength materials and magnetic bearing technology that this approach has garnered increased interest. The exploration of high-strength materials has enabled designers to achieve higher operating speeds,

consequently yielding greater kinetic energy storage capacities. Meanwhile, the integration of magnetic bearings has facilitated the attainment of these high operating speeds, resulting in cleaner, faster, and more efficient bearing systems capable of functioning under extreme temperature conditions. Recent advancements in flywheel design hold the potential for significant improvements in performance and service life, as well as the provision of substantial control torques and momentum storage capacities. Such capabilities are particularly relevant in applications involving spacecraft, launch vehicles, aircraft power systems, and power supplies. **Material Strength:**

The choice of materials plays a pivotal role in determining the effectiveness and durability of flywheels. Stronger materials possess the ability to withstand higher operating stresses, enabling them to function at elevated rotational speeds. This characteristic is essential for maximizing energy storage capacity, as higher rotational speeds equate to increased stored energy. However, it's imperative to note that while stronger materials allow for greater energy storage potential, they also need to be carefully balanced with considerations for material failure and structural integrity.

Rotational Speed

The rotational speed of a flywheel directly influences the amount of energy it can store. Higher rotational speeds translate to greater energy storage capacity. However, the relationship between rotational speed and energy storage is not linear, as excessively high speeds can impose significant mechanical loads on both the flywheel and associated bearings. Therefore, optimizing rotational speed is crucial to strike a balance between maximizing energy storage and ensuring the structural integrity of the system.

Geometry:

The geometric design of the flywheel plays a crucial role in determining its specific energy, which refers to its kinetic energy storage capability per unit mass or volume. Optimizing the geometry, such as the shape and cross-sectional profile, can lead to substantial improvements in the flywheel's kinetic energy storage capacity. By enhancing the geometry, it's possible to reduce overall loads on the shaft and bearings while minimizing the risk of material failure. This optimization process is essential for maximizing the efficiency and performance of flywheel systems across various applications.

II. METHODOLOGIES

CATIA (Computer Aided Three-dimensional Interactive Application) is a multi-platform CAD/CAM/CAE commercial software suite developed by the French company

Assault Systems. Written in the C++ programming language, CATIA is the cornerstone of the Assault Systems product lifecycle management software suite. The design of a flywheel can vary significantly, ranging from simplistic forms like a solid cylindrical disc to more intricate structures resembling conventional wheels with spokes or arms connecting a central hub to a peripheral rim. Even among small flywheels, there's diversity, with some being solid discs possessing a hollow circular cross-section.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main objective of this investigation is to do The tetrahedral element described here exhibits quadratic displacement behavior and is particularly well-adapted for modeling irregular meshes, which are commonly generated from various CAD/CAM systems. This element is characterized by ten nodes, each possessing three degrees of freedom: translations

along the x, y, and z axes. Additionally, the element is equipped with capabilities for plasticity, creep, swelling, stress stiffening, large deflection, and large strain, enhancing its versatility and applicability in modeling complex structural phenomena.

Fig. 2 Re plotting (Refresh) the component from the menu bar

Fig. 3 Meshing Flywheel

1. Results of Displacement Analysis:

Fig: 4 Displacement of Flywheel Assembly

Fig: 5. Displacement of Flywheel Ring Gear

2. Structural Analysis Results for Flywheel

Fig. 6. Displacement of Flywheel Assembly

Fig. 7. Displacement of Flywheel Ring Gear

CONCLUSION

The analysis indicates that our goal of assessing the effects of varying loads on the flywheel within the Petrol Engine, particularly under variable speeds, has been achieved. The design has proven to be successful in meeting the intended objectives.

Structural Analysis

S.No	Results	Flywheel Assembly	Flywheel Ring Gear
01	Displacement (in mm)	0.59023	0.38516
02	Stress (MPa)	788.316	507.343
03	Strain (MPa)	0.005101	0.002804

As depicted in the figures above, the comprehensive assembly design of the flywheel has undergone meshing and analysis using Ansys software. The obtained results reveal minimal displacement in both the flywheel assembly and the flywheel ring gear. This indicates that each component within the assembly experiences only minor displacement.

Moreover, the stress observed at the fixing location is minimal, well within acceptable limits, and significantly below the yield point. This demonstrates that the stress levels are well within the safety margins dictated by the design parameters.

Dynamic Analysis

S.No	Results	CI – 3500	AI – 3500	CI – 10000	AI – 10000
01	Displacement (in mm)	0.06453	0.046287	0.092166	0.13414
02	Displacement Rot. (in mm)	0.069947	0.003373	0.099926	0.476717
03	Von Misses Stress (MPa)	657.472	518.968	937.93	1504.49
04	Von Misses Strain (MPa)	0.003742	0.003373	0.005345	0.009779

Furthermore, the maximum strain, as determined through the Ansys software, is also found to be very low. This underscores the robustness of the design, as it operates comfortably below critical strain thresholds.

In conclusion, the analysis results validate the accuracy of the design parameters. The strain exerted on the designed model, particularly at the fixing location, falls well within acceptable ranges, affirming the overall effectiveness and reliability of the design.

The design of the flywheel within the Petrol Engine, featuring a mechanism capable of accommodating variable speeds, has demonstrated flawless performance during analysis. These successful outcomes underscore the fulfillment of our objective to a remarkable degree

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